

Promotion in Mexico of the hermetic metal silo to minimize stored grain losses

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Abstract

This publication reports on the experience of CIMMYT promoting hermetically sealed metal silos to minimize losses in stored maize and other grains under smallholder farming conditions in Mexico. The metal silo was developed through the "Postcosecha" project first implemented in the 1980s in Central America and introduced in Mexico in the 1990s. The hermetic metal silo promoted in Mexico has evolved into a more advanced version with a conical upper shape and the use of bronze or aluminum plugs to increase airtightness and eliminate the need to use poisonous aluminum phosphide tablets. Through CIMMYT and Mexican partnerships, the manufacturing process for the silos has been established in a Mexican Norm to standardize the dimensions. CIMMYT and its network of collaborators have been promoting the hermetic metal silo through the hub model. Farmers typically store maize grain in woven polypropylene bags with or without chemical insecticides; grain damage can reach 32%, in tropical conditions after three months of storage. In side-by-side comparisons of the hermetic metal silo and farmers' practices, the hermetic metal silo kept losses to less than 3%. Local artisans were trained in manufacturing the silos and to facilitate access of smallholder farmers to the technology, but the lack of awareness, business models, and credits have hindered the widespread adoption of hermetic metal silos. Promotion of the hermetic metal silo, including stakeholder collaboration leading to institutional anchoring, should continue, to reduce storage losses and to safeguard farm households' food security, health, and profits.

Keywords: postharvest; storage losses; hermetic metal silo; grain; pests.

Introduction

In Mexico, postharvest losses for maize grain in smallholder farming conditions are estimated at more than 20%, particularly during storage, when they can reach 60% in tropical regions after six months of storage (Odjo et al., 2020). Losses are generally caused by insect pests such as the larger grain borer *Prostephanus truncatus* (Horn) (Coleoptera: Bostrichidae) or the maize weevil *Sitophilus zeamais* (Motschulsky), as well as fungi and rodents. In Mexico, farmers generally protect their grain with pesticides, such as aluminum phosphide tablets or deodorized malathion at high dosages (González Regalado et al., 2017), but without great success (Odjo et al., 2020). Other causes of postharvest losses include poor postharvest practices, lack of access to equipment such as shellers and dryers, or labor shortages; particularly during peak harvesting periods, when grain needs to be gathered, processed, and securely stored as quickly as possible to avoid damage by the aforementioned pests.

Airtight containers sealed to keep grain dry and secure can minimize storage losses in smallholder farming systems. The concept harks back to the underground pits used to store harvests by prehistoric farmers and emerged from efforts to develop affordable solutions for smallholder farmers (Baributsa and Concepcion Ignacio, 2020). The effectiveness of hermetic technologies in preserving stored grain has been demonstrated in Mexico (García-Lara et al., 2020; Odjo et al., 2022b, 2022a), Kenya (De Groote et al., 2013; Ndegwa et al., 2016), and Bangladesh (Krupnik et al., 2022).

Any airtight container — for example, plastic bags or recycled jerrycans, water bottles — can serve the purpose, but hermetic bags and metal silos have gained the attention of farmers and development programs. Hermetic plastic bags generally comprise an inner liner, which can be single or double and made of a multilayered film designed as a gas barrier and to create hypoxia conditions, and an additional outer layer, generally of woven polypropylene, sometimes treated with an insecticide (Baributsa and Concepcion Ignacio, 2020).

The metal silo is a cylindrical container of galvanized sheets with secure lids or seals to prevent the entry of air and pests. When the silos are properly sealed, any pests that may have gotten in with the grain soon deplete existing oxygen and suffocate (Tefera et al., 2011). The origin of the metal silo can be traced back to the "POSTCOSECHA" project of the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), which introduced this technology in Honduras, Guatemala, Nicaragua and El Salvador in the 1980s (Bravo Martínez, 2009; Hellin and Kanampiu, 2008). Through this project, hundreds of thousands of silos were disseminated to millions of farmers, with positive impacts on farmers' food security and income. The institutional anchor of this technology and the involvement of non-governmental organizations contributed to the dissemination of the metal silos in the targeted countries and beyond, even after the SDC project stopped in 2013 (Bokusheva et al., 2012; Tefera et al., 2011)

The metal silo was probably introduced in Mexico as an indirect benefit of the POSTCOSECHA project. Bravo Martínez (2009) mentioned that in the 1990s, the project generated interest in neighboring countries, with Guatemalan tinsmiths trained by the project delivering flat-type metal silos in the border zone of Mexico or emigrating to Mexico to manufacture silos there. The International Maize and Wheat

Improvement Center (CIMMYT) started work on the metal silo probably in the late 1990s, under a participatory research program during which the technology was introduced for testing by smallholder farmers, who ended up purchasing the models they tested (Hellin et al., 2005).

Partnering with Mexico's agriculture secretariat in the 2010s, CIMMYT implemented MasAgro, a program involving the federal government, national research institutions, and local communities to refine and deliver innovations with farmers and promote sustainable agriculture. The program set up "hubs," in major eco-regions to capture farmers' needs and concerns and co-create locally-adapted solutions (Liedtka et al., 2017), offering farmers and other stakeholders direct agency in the research agenda. They typically featured platforms implemented with local research institutions to develop recommendations adapted to the local context; modules with innovative farmers which are side-by-side comparisons between proposed innovations and conventional practices and extension areas to foster interactions among farmers of local communities (Camacho-Villa et al., 2016; Gardezabal et al., 2023). Initially focusing on conservation agriculture, MasAgro evolved to include topics such as postharvest management, including the metal silo. Challenges noted included 1) poor standardization in the silos promoted in Mexico, reducing farmer confidence in their effectiveness; 2) a lack of data on the effectiveness of the silos, particularly on-farm as well as technical support and training materials; and 3) insufficient supplies of silos in most rural areas and few local artisans trained in their manufacture.

This paper reports on the experience of MasAgro and other related CIMMYT-led projects to test and promote the use of hermetic metal silos in Mexico, including standardizing their materials and design, assessing their effectiveness in different agro-ecologies, training local artisans to manufacture them, and fostering a manufacturer network.

Characteristics of the Mexican hermetic metal silo

The first mentions of the metal silo in Mexico can be traced back to the mid-to-late 90s. However, there is a difference in the type of silos that spread in Mexico. The silos promoted by POSTCOSECHA had flat tops and bottoms, were not totally hermetic, and farmers were advised to use them with tablets of aluminum phosphide, a hazardous insecticide. Eventually an upper conical cup (García-Lara et al., 2007) and a bronze plug were introduced in the design to increase airtightness and eliminate the need for aluminum phosphide. The development of this version of the hermetic metal silo (called in this document **hermetic metal silo**) was supported by tinsmiths, various governmental and non-governmental organizations, and initiatives dedicated to reducing postharvest losses and improving food security in Mexico, including CIMMYT and Mexico's National Institute of Forestry, Agriculture, and Livestock Research (INIFAP). CIMMYT and 11 Mexican institutions led an initiative that resulted in establishment of a Mexican norm stipulating a standard manufacturing process and characteristics for the hermetic metal silo (NMX-FF-123-SCFI-2015 Norma Mexicana, 2015).

According to the norm, the hermetic metal silo is a cylindrical container with a capacity of from 25 to 2,000 kg, made of gauge 24-26 galvanized sheets bonded to ensure complete airtightness, with an upper opening for grain loading and a lower outlet to remove grain (Fig. 1, 2). These openings, with a male (upper) and a female (lower) thread, are closed by a plug made of bronze, aluminum, or galvanized sheeting with a polytetrafluoroethylene (Teflon) film and a thin rubber gasket ring to ensure a hermetic seal. The plugs are manufactured by other craftsmen specializing in bronze and aluminum work, which is made possible thanks to the standardized dimensions of the diameter of the hermetic metal silo openings as well as the plugs (Fig. 1). The hermetic metal silo is generally delivered to farmers with its plugs, a spanner adapted to the plug, and a funnel for grain filling.

Fig 1. Hermetic metal silos of different capacities (on the left); different plugs in bronze and aluminum and a thin rubber rope used to seal hermetic metal silos and to guarantee airtightness in Mexico.

Legend: ∅: diameter; P: perimeter; R: radius

Fig 2. Dimensions of a hermetic metal silo with a capacity of 1,000 kg of grain as defined by the Mexican Norm NMX-FF-123-SCFI-2015 (Norma Mexicana, 2015). Additional plans are provided in supplemental materials 1 to 3.

The norm specifies the correct assembly, proper welding of all joints, the materials to use, and other specs to ensure permanent and complete sealing. Also noted is the need to fully test the seal and inspect all joints, parts, and plugs for pores or holes. CIMMYT has developed a step-by-step hermeticity test using compressed air (Vargas Lara et al., 2019).

Data on the effectiveness of hermetic metal silo in minimizing storage losses in different Mexican states

During 2017-18 CIMMYT conducted experiments to promote varied grain storage methods. Odjo et al. (2020) reported on "non-controlled" on-farm experiment at 47 sites in 2017 and 58 sites in 2018 over 12 states of Mexico, comparing farmers' storage practices — typically, woven polypropylene bags with or without pesticides such as aluminum phosphide or deodorized malathion — vs improved innovations, including the hermetic metal silo. The data for these experiments were published by Verhulst et al. (2020) and used to compute average storage losses, meaning the percentage of undamaged grain at the moment of storage vs the percentage for the stored grain withdrawn at the end of the experiment, for conventional technologies and the hermetic metal silo. Storage times, which differed for each participating farmer, were adjusted to 90 days of storage per state, extrapolating a linear increase/decrease in associated losses (Fig. 3; supplemental material 4).

Losses were highest in grain stored in woven polypropylene bags, whose permeability allows easy entry of moisture (Abass et al., 2018; Chigoverah and Mvumi, 2016; De Groot et al., 2013; García-Lara et al., 2019; Odjo et al., 2022a), with an overall average of 16% after 90 days of storage and as high as 32% as in Oaxaca (Fig. 3). Pest pressure and associated grain damage under farmer storage practices tends to be considerably higher in tropical regions (Odjo et al., 2020). Significant damage was also recorded in grain stored using polypropylene bags with aluminum phosphide tablets (15% in Chiapas; 6% overall in Mexico), even using high insecticide dosages. Treatment with deodorized malathion was much more effective, reducing losses to 1% overall in Mexico. Many problems are associated with the use of chemicals by smallholder farmers for grain storage. First, most smallholders lack adequate materials or training in handling chemicals, bringing a high risk of direct or indirect poisoning of humans and animals. Malathion, for example, is a carcinogen, with oxidative, inflammatory, neurotoxic, hepatotoxic, and nephrotoxic effects; even at low doses its intake can damage the human endocrine and reproductive systems (Badr, 2020) and its use by smallholders should be discouraged (Odjo et al., 2020). In addition, the chemicals' effectiveness, particularly in the case of aluminum phosphide, diminishes over long storage as insects pass through different developmental stages and some (eggs and pupae, for example) may be less affected by insecticides (Howe, 1973; Manandhar et al., 2018; Odjo et al., 2020).

Storage losses with hermetic metal silos were low — around 2% overall for Mexico — and are similar to results achieved with hermetic bags and other alternative hermetic technologies. De Groot et al. (2013) reported results from trials in Kenya where low levels of grain infestation and damage were achieved when the metal silo was used in combination with Actellic Super (a.i. $\frac{1}{4}$ Pirimiphos-methyl 16 g/kg β Permethrin 3 g/kg) or with Phostoxin (a.i. $\frac{1}{4}$ aluminum phosphide, 57% w/w). Results from Mexico demonstrated that careful manufacturing can ensure a hermetic seal and rapid hypoxia in insects hidden in the stored grain, thus obviating the need for chemicals. Odjo et al. (2020) reported a case where damage to the hermetic metal silo was relatively high and highlighted the importance of training for local tinsmiths in producing high-quality silos.

Legend: HMS: hermetic metal silo; PP: polypropylene bag; PP_AP: Polypropylene bag with aluminum phosphide; PP_DM: polypropylene bag with deodorized malathion.

Fig. 3. Average storage losses (% damage at the beginning vs % damage at the end of the storage period) adjusted to 90 days of storage, for different storage technologies and several states of Mexico.

Facilitating smallholder farmers' access to the hermetic metal silo: training local artisans and promotion in Mexico

The hermetic metal silo has been promoted via hubs, particularly in Central and Southern Mexico where postharvest losses pose a huge challenge, according to smallholder farmers. Rather than focusing only on introducing an innovation, the hub approach aims for sustainable systemic change that includes profitability and resilience, integrating co-creation and knowledge exchange with farmers and working closely with input and machinery suppliers (Gardeazabal et al., 2023).

Hermetic metal silo suppliers, including tinsmiths, are a critical part of the network. During 2013 to 2019, 67 local artisans received training organized by CIMMYT on the manufacture of hermetic metal silos following the Mexican standard and including instruction on basic marketing and postharvest practices.

CIMMYT follows up with these tinsmiths each year regarding their activities and maintains and shares an updated list of postharvest technology suppliers. Of the 67 tinsmiths who received training, only 16 are still manufacturing silos. The other tinsmiths cited a lack of demand (70%) or the lack of capital (21%) as their main reasons for stopping. Other reasons included a shortage of labor, the low availability of materials, and a lack of awareness among farmers and training for using and managing silos. Nearly all the "inactive" tinsmiths said local demand for silos and access to credit need to improve, for them to begin manufacturing silos again. Gitonga et al. (2013) reported similar results in Kenya, where only four out of 40 local artisans were still manufacturing metal silos after training, due to a lack of demand and farmer awareness. Similar to Kenya, tinsmiths in Mexico generally sell hermetic metal silos of 500 and 1,000 kg capacity to individual farmers, NGOs, and government programs. Even though the surveyed tinsmiths mentioned the lack of demand as a risk for the market, they also cited the need for a certification process to ensure silo quality and, thereby, farmer confidence in the innovation.

The adoption of the hermetic metal silo in Mexico suffers the same challenges as for scaling other innovations among smallholder farmers in low- and middle-income countries, including physical and economic accessibility. Hermetic metal silos are relatively expensive and the cost of adopting this technology can be a significant barrier for small-scale farmers and rural communities with limited financial resources, as documented by Gitonga et al. (2013) in Kenya. The same authors suggested that raising awareness, promotion through farmers' popular media (e.g., radio in local languages), and training can help enhance the adoption of hermetic metal silos. However, there is also a need to develop sustainable business models for hermetic metal silos that can foster their affordability.

Conclusion

Postharvest losses remain an important challenge to hundred thousand of smallholder farmers in Mexico. Storage losses due to insects, fungi and rodents can be as high as 32% after three months of storage, which endangers their food security. The hermetic metal silo, an airtight storage system that creates an

oxygen-depleted environment, is one of the technologies promoted by CIMMYT. In Mexico, the hermetic metal silo was introduced in the 90s. Its design has evolved to achieve a version that works on the sole principle of hermeticity without the need to use any conditioning agents. Through a collaborative effort between CIMMYT and various local institutions, a Mexican norm that defines the hermetic metal's manufacturing process has been established. Experiments in Mexico have demonstrated its effectiveness in minimizing storage losses regardless of the agroecologies.

The widespread adoption of hermetic metal silos by smallholder farmers in Mexico has yet to occur, owing to a lack of awareness among farmers, of local demand, and of sustainable business models for scaling the technology. Collaborative efforts to promote hermetic metal silos (even beyond Mexico) should continue through awareness raising campaigns, providing training and technical support, offering financial assistance, and ensuring proper distribution and accessibility. Strengthening tinsmiths' associations can enhance the marketing and promotion of metal silos, as well as self-regulation in maintaining high-quality standards.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplemental Material 1. Dimensions of a hermetic metal silo with a capacity of 100 kg of grain

Legend: \varnothing : diameter; P: perimeter; R: radius

Supplemental material 2. Dimensions of a hermetic metal silo with a capacity of 500 kg of grain

Legend: ϕ : diameter; P: perimeter; R: radius

Supplemental material 3. Dimensions of a hermetic metal silo with a capacity of 2,000 kg of grain

Legend: \varnothing : diameter; P: perimeter; R: radius

Supplemental material 4. Average storage losses (adjusted to 90 days of maize storage in different Mexican states. Experiments were performed between 2017 and 2018. Data were derived from Verhulst et al., 2020.

States	Storage technologies	N	Average storage loss	SD.S	SD.P
Chiapas	HMS	13	2.2	2.13	2.05
	PP	6	10.8	10.98	10.02
	PP_AP	6	15.4	14.31	13.06
	PP_DM	6	0.6	0.55	0.50
Chihuahua	HMS	15	1.4	3.04	2.93
	PP	21	9.2	11.25	10.98
	PP_AP	2	8.0	9.29	6.57
Estado de México	HMS	3	3.1	2.90	2.37
	PP	1	0.8	-	-
	PP_AP	1	15.3	-	-
Hidalgo	HMS	3	0.3	0.33	0.27
	PP	1	29.8	-	-
Jalisco	HMS	3	0.1	0.16	0.13
	PP_AP	1	2.6	3.05	2.16
Michoacán	HMS	2	0.0	-	-
	PP	1	0.0	-	-
	PP_AP	1	1.7	-	-
Morelos	HMS	1	4.0	-	-
	PP	1	4.3	-	-
	PP_AP	2	1.8	-	-
Oaxaca	HMS	26	2.2	2.84	2.78
	PP	17	32.3	25.30	24.55
	PP_AP	18	2.8	2.89	2.81
	PP_DM	1	0.0	-	-
Puebla	HMS	5	1.2	0.88	0.79
	PP	1	6.2	-	-
	PP_DM	3	2.3	1.54	1.25
Querétaro	HMS	1	0.0	-	-
	PP	2	0.3	0.38	0.27
Tlaxcala	HMS	2	0.61	0.59	0.41
	PP	2	0.00	-	-
Yucatán	HMS	9	2.3	3.02	2.85
	PP	11	17.8	20.32	19.37
Mexico (country)	HMS	83	1.8	2.54	2.52
	PP	65	16.2	19.85	19.70
	PP_AP	31	5.8	8.46	8.32
	PP_DM	10	1.1	1.21	1.15

Legend: SD.S: Standard Deviation for the Sample; SD.P: Standard Deviation for the Population; HMS: Hermetic Metal Silo; PP: Polypropylene bag; PP_AP: Polypropylene bag with Aluminum Phosphide; PP_DM: Polypropylene bag with Deodorized Malathion.